

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

BIOACCUMULATION OF NICKEL IONS IN TOMATO AND CUCUMBER ORGANS

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ABSTRACT

When observing the bioaccumulation of nickel ions in the plant organs of tomatoes and cucumbers, the highest amounts are mainly in the roots, from 5.94 mg/kg to 7.60 mg/kg of contaminated soil in tomatoes, 11.88-15.19 times the MPC, and less in cucumber roots compared to tomato roots. bioaccumulation was observed, 3.35-5.38 mg/kg, and 6.71 to 10.77 times higher bioaccumulation than MPC. This situation is the opposite in the stem part, where bioaccumulation was observed in tomato plant stem up to 2.58 times MPC, and in cucumber up to 5.00 times, in leaves 1.88-3.28 times MPC in tomato and 1.45-1.93 times in cucumber leaves, respectively. During the experiments, bioaccumulation of 1.05 mg/kg was found in both plants in the fruits of the plant, which was found to be 2.10 times higher than MPC on average, forming the following decreasing ecological series:

- in tomato organs - root→leaf→fruit→stem;
- in cucumber organs - root→stem→fruit→leaf.

Keywords: Soil, heavy metals, tomatoes, cucumbers.

Introduction. Soil contamination with toxic heavy metals (HM) is a serious global environmental problem. In recent years, especially in developing countries, air pollution has been increasing due to rapid urbanization, industrial activity and traffic density. Consumption of vegetables grown in urban centers with high levels of traffic-related pollution poses a significant risk to human health due to the HM contained in these plants. HM has a toxic and carcinogenic effect on the human body even when consumed in low concentrations.

Literature review. Currently, the increase in the amount of toxicants in the soil is causing their bioaccumulation in large quantities in food products grown in agriculture.

Nickel is one of the important elements for soil and plants, and it is required by scientists to determine its various concentrations and bioaccumulation in agricultural crops according to soil contamination with toxicants.

HM exists naturally in different background states worldwide due to its variable concentrations in rocks. Some HM are used as essential trace elements to complete the life cycle of plants (respiration, photosynthesis, etc.) and have toxic effects [1, p. 869-881.]. Correia L. et al. tomatoes were grown in soils with nickel amounts of 0, 35, 70, and 105 mg/kg, and nickel concentrations in roots, stems, leaves, and fruits were measured at four different stages of the cycle. As a result, it was determined that the concentration of nickel found in the fruit is too low to pose a risk to human health [4, p. 1-12.]. Nickel has been implicated in the substitution of Ni²⁺ for Fe²⁺ in iron dioxygenases, causing various diseases in human health such as allergy, cardiovascular and renal diseases, pulmonary fibrosis, lung and nasal cancer [6. P. 286-293.].

Soil contamination with toxic HM is a serious global environmental problem [10, p. 2196-2211., 7, 110593.]. According to scientists, mineral fertilizers also have different effects on OMs and their bioaccumulation in plant composition and physiological processes.

A transcriptome analysis by Yu H. et al. showed that Ni toxicity alters the expression of genes involved in carbon/nitrogen metabolism, theoretically identifying key genes that reduce excess Ni accumulation in tomato plants and are beneficial for food security and sustainable agricultural development. the basics have been developed [17, p. 1-17.].

Globally, cropland contamination with Ni, one of the OMs, poses a wide threat to the plant kingdom [7, p. 110593.]. The stress-relieving molecule melatonin (ME) is widely used to mitigate OM-induced phytotoxicity [2, p. 1842-1855.].

Phytoremediation methods carried out by plants improve the ecological status of soil composition [16; p. 133] also has a positive effect on the agroecological condition of the soil [18, S. 256.]. In some cases, application of nickel fertilizer in the soil improves urease activity in plants and reduces nitrate activity [14, p. 177.].

Scientists from Guru Nanak Dev University, India observed that Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) has low sugar content and low productivity of tomato due to both biotic and abiotic stress factors. Nickel (Ni) induced stress in plants [9, S. 1449-1455.].

In addition, the article is applied to biological remediation methods against nickel contamination of European soils. In conclusion, the reviewed works have shown that the effectiveness of phytoremediation can be realized with co-remediation approaches [16, S. 133.].

Roccotiello, E. et al found for the first time in the tomato plant that Ni can take up OM, changing the allergenic profile and doubling the risk of exposure for consumers [15, S. 5432.].

References. Soils for laboratory experiments were carried out on typical gray soils distributed at an altitude of 391 meters above sea level, and field experiments were carried out on the farm "Khiromiddin Nurullaevich" of Kitab district, distributed at an altitude of 672 meters above sea level. carried out in non-fertilizer options. Microvegetation "Miniature" Neibauer's experiment based on the laboratory experiment processed by Holodkovskii, 5 kg of soil was drawn into the 20 cm

long, 20 cm diagonal pots, contaminated with 7 types of HM in 3 and 5 times of the permissible norm (MPC), in addition to 7 types of elements. carried out in complex contaminated variants with specified MPCs (Table 1).

Field experiments were also conducted in two options, 4 returns, option 1 was control, option 2 was applied to tomato plants with mineral fertilizers N160P120K80, and cucumber plants with N150P100K75. During the experiment, mineral fertilizers were used for plant growth, and the determination of nutrients during the experiment was not included in the objective tasks.

Table 1

Scheme of the experiment

№	Options (in 4 returns).
1	Soil (control) + plant
2	Soil + (N160P120K80 for tomato, N150P100K75 for cucumber) (Background) + plant
3	Background+Cr MPC (3 times more) + plant
4	Background+Cr MPC (5 times more) + plant
5	Background+ Ni MPC (3 times as much) + plant
6	Background+ Ni MPC (5 times more) + plant
7	Background+ Cd MPC (3 times more) + plant
8	Background+ Cd MPC (5 times more) + plant
9	Background+ So MPC (3 times as much) + plant
10	Background+ So MPC (5 times more) + plant
11	Background+ Pb MPC (3 times more) + plant
12	Background+ Pb MPC (5 times more) + plant
13	Background+ Cu MPC (3 times more) + plant
14	Background+ Cu MPC (5 times more) + plant
15	Background+ Zn MPC (3 times more) + plant
16	Background+ Zn MPC (5 times more) + plant
17	Background+complex effect (3 times more) + plant
18	Background+complex effect (5 times more) + plant
19	Field soil without fertilizer + plant
20	Field soil with mineral fertilizers Soil + (N160P120K80 for tomatoes, N150P100K75 for cucumbers)

In the field experiment, for tomatoes and cucumbers, attention was paid to the following, and the planting scheme of tomatoes was carried out in a 70x30-30 scheme, 2 options and 4 returns. 1 return is 4 rows, width 0.7 x 4=2.8 m length 20 m 2.8x20=56 m². 4th return 56 m²x4=224 m². 2 options 4 returns 224m²x2=448 m².

Cucumbers were planted in the 70x140-40 scheme and carried out in 2 options and 4 returns. 1 return in 4 rows width 0.7 x 1.40 x0.7x1.40=4.2 m length 20 m 4.2x20=84 m². 4th return 84 m²x4=336 m². 2 options 4

returns 336 m²x2=672 m². 2 variants of tomatoes and cucumbers, the total area of 4 returns is 672+448 m²=1120 m².

Conducted field and laboratory experiments were made into 10 options in order to compare options based on one element and analyzed based on the following table (Table 2).

Chromium ion content in tomato and cucumber plant organs was determined using an AVIO-200 spectrometer in absorption obtained in 1 percent nitric acid.

Table 2

Options selected for the purpose of comparing the first table base and field experiences

№	Options
1	Plant organ (control)
2	Plant Organ (N160P120K80 for tomato, N150P100K75 for cucumber) (Background)
3	Background + element MPC (3 times) plant organ
4	Background + element MPC (5 times) plant organ
5	Background + complex effect (3 times) plant organ
6	Background + complex effect (5 times) plant organ
7	Field soil + plant organ
8	Field soil + (N160P120K80 for tomato, N150P100K75 for cucumber) plant organ
9	Field experiment + plant organ
10	Field experiment + (N160P120K80 for tomato, N150P100K75 for cucumber) plant organ

The MPC of mobile nickel in soil is 4 mg/kg, and the MPC of 0.5 mg/kg for vegetables and pulse crops [19, C. 62., 20, 54 c.].

In laboratory and field experiments fed with control and mineral fertilizers, there was no increase in nickel MPC in the roots of both plants.

In option 3, where artificial pollution was carried out, when nickel was polluted 3 times more than MPC, during the years (2021-2023), tomato roots were 6.80-5.02-6.00 (average 5.94±0.89) mg/kg, 5 7.54-8.35-6.90 (average 7.60±0.73) mg/kg in variant 4, which is 3 times more contaminated than the complex MPC of elements, variant 5, which is 4.22-3.61-3.73 (average 3.85±0.32) mg/kg and 4.44-4.27-3.96 (average 4.42±0.24) mg/kg in 5-fold contaminated option 6. Bioaccumulation of 3.47-3.33-3.27 mg/kg was observed in cucumber roots, and 4.18-3.62-3.32 mg/kg in option 4 (Fig. 1).

In tomato roots, it was 10.04-13.60 times higher than MPC, with an average of 5.94±0.89 mg/kg, and in option 4, which was 5 times higher, it was 13.79-16.71 times higher only in tomatoes, mineral fertilizers bioaccumulation over MPC was observed in cucumber roots in variants 5 and 6 fed with complex. Option 5 was 4.22±0.22 mg/kg in tomato roots only in 2021, which was 8.44 times higher than MPC, bioaccumulation was observed around 3.61 and 3.73 mg/kg in the following years. In all other cases, cucumber roots were contaminated with nickel 4.47-4.50 mg/kg, 5 times higher than MPC, in variant 6, less bioaccumulation was observed than tomato roots in the amount of 0.97-1.47-1.65 mg/kg, 10 times higher than MPC, 81-11.48-10.01 times higher than MPC in 2021, 2.94 times in 2022, and 2.09 times in 2023 compared to MPC in tomato roots (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Nickel bioaccumulation in tomato and cucumber roots (mg/kg during 2021-2023).

In conclusion, complex contamination of soil with other types of toxicants enhances nickel bioaccumulation as a result of the reaction of chemical elements in cucumber roots. On the other hand, in tomato roots, it is the opposite, in options 5 and 6, which are 5 times more complex than MPC, negatively affecting nickel bioaccumulation, and over the years, the amount of ions accumulated in roots from option 5 increased by 5.16←2.82→4.54 (on average 4.17) times, when comparing options 6 and 4, it was found that the difference between options was 6.20→8.17←5.87 (on average 6.75) times less (Table 3).

So, in complex pollution, it was found that Ni bioaccumulation in tomato roots is less than MPC, and vice versa in cucumber roots. It is necessary to conduct research in this regard.

As the stem part of the plant is considered to spread and distribute all the macro and micro elements absorbed from the root to all organs, the bioaccumulator organ that is next to the root after the distributed elements is the stem.

It is shown in Table 3 that in both plants as root, MPC is less than the control, variant 2 (treated with mineral fertilizers) and variants 6-10. On the contrary, in the cucumber stalk, it was found to be less than MPC in the control variant, but in variant 2 treated with mineral fertilizers, it was 1.02 to 1.40 times higher than MPC, and in field experiments, bioaccumulation was observed 2.07-1.43 times higher than MPC.

Due to the bioaccumulation of the root system, in the stem part of the tomato, compared to the root, in the 3rd option, the amount is 6.16 mg/kg in 2021, 4.48

mg/kg in 2022, and 4.93 mg/kg in 2023, and in the 4th option 6.42-7.35-5.17 mg/kg was found to be low.

From the soils of option 5, which is 3 times more than MPC, in 2022, it is 1.12 times higher than MPC, and in option 6, which is 5 times higher, it is 0.91-0.73-0.68 over the years (average 0.77 ± 0.12) mg/kg is less and 1.54 times higher than REM (Table 3).

In cucumber stalks, over the years it was found that 4.67-6.82-3.52 times higher than MPC in variant 3, and 2.06-2.98-2.32 times higher in nickel in variant 5 times higher than MPC. In case of complex contamination, bioaccumulation after the first year of experiments was 2.21-1.02-0.45 (average 1.23 ± 0.90) mg/kg in stems and 3.16-1.56-0.37 (average 1.90 ± 1.13) mg/kg less, bioaccumulation was observed 4.43-2.03-0.91 and 6.31-3.13-1.94 times higher than MPC (Table 1).

On average, nickel in tomato stems is less than the bioaccumulation MPC, in cucumber stems it is 2.34-3.41-1.76 (average 2.50 ± 0.84) mg/kg in option 3, in complex contaminated options it is 2.21 and 3 in 2021 .16 mg/kg (Figure 2).

In conclusion, the bioaccumulation of nickel from the root in the stems was observed only in cucumber, in 2022 the bioaccumulation of 3.41 mg/kg was observed in the option contaminated with nickel 3 times higher than MPC, 6.82 times higher than MPC, and 5 times higher than MPC in variant 6 in 2021 It was 6.31 times higher than MPC, and 3.13-1.94 times more Ni bioaccumulation (3.79 than MPC on average) was observed in the following years.

Figure 2. bioaccumulation of nickel in tomato and cucumber stems, mg/kg

For both plant species, higher concentrations of Ni were observed in above-ground organs than in roots, but higher Ni bioaccumulation was observed in tomato than in cucumber [11, p. 155-172.].

During the studies, bioaccumulation lower than MPC was observed in leaf organs in the first and second options fed with mineral fertilizers. Bioaccumulation of

nickel in the range of 0.88-1.40 mg/kg was observed in cucumber leaves of 7-10 variants obtained in 2022, which was 1.75-2.79 times higher than MPC (Fig. 3).

In conclusion, it can be said that compared to tomatoes, the bioaccumulation of nickel in cucumber leaves is 1.39-1.93 times higher than MPC in different conditions.

Figure 3. Average bioaccumulation of nickel ion in tomato and cucumber plant leaves during 2021-2023, mg/kg

Nickel has both negative and positive aspects compared to other elements, with sandy soils requiring nickel levels below 10 mg/kg, while clay soils require higher levels of 45 and 60 mg/kg soil. Increasing soil content from 30 mg to 45 mg and increasing to 60 mg/kg soil had negative effects [12, p. 40-45.]. The amount of nickel in tomato buds and fruits increases with its growth, and the amount of nickel in the fruits reaches about 0.15-10.5 mg/kg [3, p. 609-626]. It is known that the amount of daily nickel requirement for human nutrition varies between 25-35 mg. Nevertheless, in controlled European and German cities, adult

nickel consumption reached 142-222 mg/day. Daily consumption of tomato fruits does not exceed a few grams [5, 286-293.]. In order to reduce the amount of nitrate and ammonium in tomato fruits, when added to nickel-deficient soils, it reduces their bioaccumulation in plants [8, 1-9.].

Due to the fact that the nickel content in the soil is less than MPC, the bioaccumulation of Ni ions is around 0.22-0.41 mg/kg in tomatoes and 0.21-0.33 mg/kg in cucumber fruits in control, mineral-treated 2nd and 7-10 options observed.

Figure 4. Average nickel bioaccumulation in tomatoes and cucumbers for 2021-2023, mg/kg

0.61-0.80 (average 0.69 ± 0.10) mg/kg of tomato fruit in options 3 and 5 contaminated with nickel 3 times more than MPC from 0.50-0.90 (average 0.71 ± 0.20) around mg/kg, 1.22-1.59 times to 1.0-1.80 times MPC, and 0.82-0.99 (average 0.91 ± 0.09) in options 4 and 6 contaminated 5 times) and 0.87-1.40 (mean 1.05 ± 0.30) mg/kg, 1.65-1.98 and 1.74-2.80 times higher bioaccumulation was observed than MPC (Figure 4).

The bioaccumulation of nickel ions in cucumber fruit was 0.76 ± 0.19 and 0.71 ± 0.14 mg/kg on average over the years in variants 3 and 5, which were 3 times more polluted than MPC, 1.51-1.42 times more than MPC, 5 and in options 4 and 6, which were twice as polluted, on average 1.05 ± 0.38 mg/kg, 1.13 ± 0.34 mg/kg, 2.11-2.27 times more than MPC (Table 1).

In conclusion, it was found that the bioaccumulation of nickel ions in tomato and cucumber plant organs is similar. The high accumulation of elemental ions in both plant organs with the progress of high bioaccumulation processes in the roots was found during the researches to form the following descending series:

- in tomato organs - root→leaf→fruit→stem;
- in cucumber organs - root→stem→fruit→leaf.

In the distribution of nickel ions on the organs of vegetable and polyps crops, the 3rd number of the crop leads to the attention of the product grower to soil recultivation.

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